

Designing of Patch Antenna By using T slot for Bandwidth Enhancement for wideband Application

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Abstract- This paper proposed the microstrip patch antenna with a T shape slot in a Exciting patch of an microstrip patch antenna for C and X band application. The proposed design is optimized by using FR4 substrate and IE3D software. The design is suitable for Wi-Max and WLAN frequency band. The substrate is used for reducing the dielectric losses and improving the performance of proposed design. The structure are used in a excited patch is simple and easy to used. The thickness between ground plan and exciting patch is 1.5mm. The proposed design is used for 10 Ghz. For this geometry we achieved Bandwidth 75.79 % for VSWR<2, minimum return loss= - 26dB, and maximum directivity 6 dBi. The Bandwidth of proposed antenna for C and X band is investigated.

Keywords—FR4, WLAN, coaxial feed, T shape slot dual band, MOM Software.

I. Introduction

For huge concert, mobility necessity and multiple band in broad band communication application The requirement of small size, low profile and different operating band antenna is demand for current scenario. Microstrip patch antenna is one of the solutions for low profile and compact size. Microstrip patch antenna consists of a substrate that is divided in to different conducting layer commonly known as patch which is etched on substrate. Many design and publication they are describe their implementation on the basis of compact and bandwidth enhancement so that it can be easily used [7]. The antenna for an X band is investigated by using ESPAR technique to improve the gain as well as bandwidth the bandwidth is less but gain has to be improve for X band application and WLAN communications [1] the other technique which is used in a wireless communication is by using a techniques of shorting pin and a V-shaped slot are applied to a rectangular microstrip patch antenna. The antenna is operated in two transverse modes TM₁₀ and TM₂₀. Such mode is using shorting pins on a rectangular patch and one additional mode TM₁₁ is obtained by V shape slot is printed on a exciting patch of an antenna. These three resonances found in the operating frequency bandwidth resulted in a wideband characteristic. [1-3] [10-12]. The author is investigated such antenna is applicable for indoor base station antennas for WLAN communication [2]. Many researchers are work on low-profile antenna arrays [7]–[9] for the broad band applications. These examples [7]–[9] are useful and simple to implement but their bandwidths are narrow. It is chosen to use for wideband antennas [4]–[5] for means of wireless communications. The i bandwidth of an antennas is investigated [1]–[5] can be used in a selected frequency apart from of other factors, like moisturizer changing. In addition, some antennas have a multiband are [2] frequently used for the

X band communications. Such antenna is work on a parasitic element to improve gain as well as bandwidth but the bandwidth is not upto the mark[2] Currently, wireless access in vehicular environments are generally referring to the standard of IEEE 802.11p is proposed. A number of microstrip or low profile antennas operating at 2.4 GHz and 5.8 GHz [7]–[9][12]. The approach is used for proposed design is to improve bandwidth in dual band and reduction in size for C and X band application. The designed antenna is suitable for 5GHz to 12GHZ. The antenna by using T shape slot in a existing patch are generally applicable for WLAN and X band Communication by tuning the slot of a proposed design the author can change the gain and bandwidth of a proposed antenna. The bandwidth of a microstrip patch antenna is achieved a 14.20% [2]-[3] similarly by changing the position and length of each slot the researcher operated in multiband [7]. By stacking of different dielectric material technique the research approach a bandwidth of 52.8% [7]

II. Mathematical Analysis

Antenna Designing:

In order to demonstrate the design of proposed antenna with a frequency range of 10GHZ, Flame Retardant 4 (FR4) substrate with relative permittivity $\epsilon_r=4.4$, and thickness (h)=1.5mm, Loss tangent ($\tan\delta$)=0.019. By mathematical analysis we can calculate different parameter of rectangular microstrip patch antenna that is ground width and length same for exciting patch of the microstrip patch antenna.[5]

$$W = \frac{c}{2f\sqrt{(\epsilon_r + 1)/2}} \quad (1)$$

$$\epsilon_{eff} = \left(\frac{\epsilon+1}{2}\right) + \left(\frac{\epsilon-1}{2}\right) \left[1 + 12 \frac{h}{W}\right]^{-1/2} \quad (2)$$

$$\Delta L = 0.412h \frac{(\epsilon_{eff} + 0.3) \left(\frac{W}{h} + 0.264\right)}{(\epsilon_{eff} + 0.258) \left(\frac{W}{h} + 0.8\right)} \quad (3)$$

$$L = \frac{c}{2f\sqrt{\epsilon_{eff}}} - 2\Delta L \quad (4)$$

$$L_g = L + 6h \quad (5)$$

$$W_g = W + 6h \quad (6)$$

where:

f = Operating frequency

ϵ_r = Permittivity of the dielectric

ϵ_{eff} = Effective permittivity of the dielectric

W = Patch's width

L = Patch's length

h = Thickness of the dielectric

L_0 = Length of ground plate

W_0 = Width of ground plate

Fig.1 (b) Geometry of Exciting patch antenna.

Fig.1(a) Geometry of ground plane with four U shape plane.

Fig.1(c) Geometry of Proposed antenna .

The geometry of ground pane and exciting patch antenna is as shown in figure 1 (a) and figure 1 (b). The proposed antenna consists of a loaded U shape slot in the ground plan and the shorting pin is connected in between excited patch and ground is as shown in figure1 (c). From the previous work the triangular patch antenna which provides a better bandwidth enhancement as compares to other work [3]. For further we can improve the bandwidth of proposed antenna we can connect a shorting pin via hole between the ground and excited patch

Table No-1:-Mathematical calculation for the proposed antenna.

S. N.	Parameters	Values for proposed antenna
1	Design frequency(f)	10GHz
2	Dielectric constant(ϵ_r)	4.3
3	Height of substrate(h)	1.5 mm
4	Loss tangent for FR4	0.019
5	Width of rectangular patch(W)	9.21442mm
6	Length of rectangular patch(L)	5.5745 mm
7	Width of ground plan (Wg)	18.2144 mm
8	Length of ground plan(Lg)	14.5774mm
9	Feed location: Xf along length),Yf(along width)	-1.50662 mm 4.6072mm

III Result Analysis and Discussion

A. Antenna Design by Using IE3D Software.

The geometry of a proposed designed is in a Flame Retardant 4 (FR4) substrate. The different antenna parameter are such as the directivity, gain,bandwidth and the radiation pattern can be obtained by using the IE3D (version 9.0) software. Based on the Software we calculated the different component of a patch from equation 1 – 6 [6] we find the length and width of rectangular microstrip patch of the proposed antenna. The different proposed antenna is suitable for WLAN, C band and X band microwave communication. The design consists of a simple T shape to improving the band width as well as directivity of the proposed antenna. The design is very easy and compact in size.

Fig. 3 D view proposed antenna

The 3 D view of proposed antenna with a probe feeding and proposed antenna.

Fig.3 Return loss curve for antenna with U slot shorting pin

For a design the antenna have two band form 5.9GHz to 6.3 GHz, and 6.4 GHz to 11.4 GHz The Return Loss for notch is effective between this two is 5 to 12GHz.From such result the design is applicable for C and X band.

Fig.5 VSWR curves for proposed antenna.

In our design we use to calculate the accurate impedance in terms of position and size of slot and thus match the impedance with 50 Ω microstrip line for maximum power transformation. Ideally, the range of voltage standing wave ratio is from zero to infinity. Practically for good performance voltage standing wave ratio must be less than two.The variations in VSWR with respect to the frequency are shown in figure (5). The VSWR is effectively less than 2 in between 5.9GHz to 6.3 GHz, and 6.4

GHz to 11.4 GHz The Return Loss for notch is effective between this two 12GHz. From such result the design is applicable for C and X band.

Fig.6 Smith chart of proposed antenna

The Smith chart shown the real and imaginary part for different frequency and by using this we calculate the reflection coefficient and impedance of the proposed antenna.

Fig.7 Directivity of a proposed antenna

The variations in Directivity with respect to the frequency are shown in figure (7). The maximum directivity is found to be 6 dBi in the operating frequency range.

Fig.9 Radiation Efficiency curve of a proposed antenna

The radiating efficiency is always greater than the antenna efficiency. Figure (9) shows that in our design maximum radiating efficiency for proposed structure is found to be 90%.

Fig.10 Axial Ratio curve of a proposed antenna

The Fig 10 shows the axial ratio of the proposed antenna. Generally the Axial ratio showed that the polarization of the proposed antenna. The fig 10 graph show the curve is below 3 dB that is our antenna work as a linear polarization

Fig.11 Elevation Pattern of a proposed antenna for 3.1 to5.5 GHz.

The radiation pattern of E field is shown in figure (11) that is radiated in omnidirection in figure of eight.

Fig.12 3D View of a proposed antenna

In fig 12 shows the 3D view of a radiation pattern of a proposed antenna.

IV. Conclusion

The microstrip patch antenna with T slot and is presented in this paper. It has been trial that by introducing the T slot the bandwidth and return loss results are enhanced. The antenna simulation is done on IE3D software. The VSWR and radiation efficiency is also achieved within suitable limit. All the parameters of proposed antenna are calculated for10 GHz frequency band. The proposed antenna obtained a band of approximately 75%, with a acceptable radiation pattern within the frequency range. The antenna is designed on FR4 substrate because of its low profile, low cost and thickness. The probe feeding technique is used.

References:-

- [1]. Reza Movahedinia, Abdel Razik, Mohmmad Reza Chahamir, "X-Band circular polarizes Electronically steerable parasitics array radiator of DRA," IEEE Transaction on Antenna and Propagation, vol.66No.2 February 2018
- [2]. Syed Muzahir abbas, Yogesh Ranga, Anand K.Verma and Karu P.Esselle, " RA Simple Ultra Wideband Printed Monopole Antenna With High Band Rejection and Wide Radiation Patterns" Ieee Transactions On Antennas And Propagation, Vol. 62, No. 9, September 2014
- [3]. Hang wong, Kwok Kan and Xia Gao, "Bandwidth Enhancement of a monopolar patch antenna V-Shape slot for car-to-car and WLAN communication", IEEE Transaction on Vehicular technology vol.18 pp 1-7,2015.
- [4]. U.Chakraborty, A.Kundu, S.K.chowdhury and A.K.Bhattacharjee "Compact Dual Band Microstrip Antenna for IEEE 802.11a WLAN application" IEEE Antenna and Wireless Propagation Letter, vol.13, no. 1, pp. 407– 411, 2014.
- [5]. D.Sugumar, Shalet Sydney, Dhanaraju Athina, T.Joyce Selvahephzibath, " Bandwidth Enhancement of coaxial feed U slotted microstrip antenna modeled with FDTD algorithm", IEEE International conference on computational intelligence and computing research, Vol. 12, 2010.
- [6]. Amer Bzeigh, Soubhi Abou Chahine, Karim Y.Kabalan, Ali EI Hajj, Ali Chehab, "Emprical Formula and Design of a broadband enhancement E patch antenna", 24th National Radio Confrence (NRSC 2007) vol. 11, 2007.
- [7]. C. A. Balanis, Antenna Theory, JohnWiley & Sons, 3rd edition, 2005.
- [8]. M. Schack, D. Kornek, E. Slotke, and T. Kürner, "Analysis of channel parameters for different antenna configurations in vehicular environments," IEEE Vehicular Technology Conf. Fall, pp. 1-5, Sep. 2010.

- [9]. L. Reichardt, J. Pontes, G. Jereczek, and T. Zwick, "Capacity maximizing MIMO antenna design for car-to-car communication," IEEE Int. Workshop on Antenna Tech., pp. 243-246, Mar. 2011.
- [10]. M. Westrick, M. Almalkawi, V. Devabhaktuni, and C. Bunting, "A low-profile, low-cost antenna system with improved gain for DSRC vehicle-to-vehicle communications," Int. Journal of RF and Microw Computer-Aided Engineering, vol. 23, no. 1, pp. 111-117, Jan. 2013.
- [11]. W. X. An, H. Wong, K. L. Lau, S. F. Li, and Q. Xue, "Design of broadband dual-band dipole for base station antenna," IEEE Trans. Antennas and Propagat., vol. 60, no. 3, pp. 1592- 1595, Mar. 2012
- [12]. J. S. Row and Y. Y. Liou, "Broadband short-circuited triangular patch antenna," IEEE Trans. Antennas and Propagat., vol. 54, no. 7, pp. 2137-2141, Jul. 2006.
- [13]. M. Rostamzadeh, S. Mohamadi, J. Nourinia, C. Ghobadi, and M. Ojaroudi, "Square monopole antenna for UWB applications with novel rod-shaped parasitic structures and novel V- shaped slots in the ground plane," IEEE Antennas and Wireless Propagat. Lett., vol. 11, pp. 446-449, 2012.
- [14]. P. F. Wu, J. M. Pei, and G. J. Liang, "A novel super thin planar car antenna," IEEE Int. Conf. on Microw. and Millimeter Wave Tech., pp. 377-379, May 2010.